

Soft set models applied to pattern recognition via 3-valued extension of neutrosophic soft sets

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In this communication, we give the theory of the 3-valued extension of neutrosophic soft set (3-valued ENSS) and define certain operations. Notably, we demonstrated an algorithm to address the decision-making problem using a soft set model. We present a similarity measure for two 3-valued ENSSs and describe its use in a pattern recognition challenge. Illustrative examples are provided to demonstrate their effectiveness in solving problems with uncertainties.

Keywords: interval valued fuzzy soft set, fuzzy soft set, decision making problem, aggregation operator.

1. Introduction

Every day, machine learning, intelligence collection, knowledge compilation, and other processes are used in the conflict resolution process. One of the biggest challenges is demonstrating the effectiveness of strategic planning. Mathematical theory enables the adoption of appropriate decision-making techniques. The DM concept might be advantageous to businesses

since it assesses and ranks different points of view based on their qualities. We can then effectively select, classify, generate, and evaluate our options. MADM considers every feature and component to provide the optimal response. It used to be widely accepted that weights and attributes required to be represented as distinct numerical values. Numerous assessments and DM problems require the analysis of numerous variables and indications. Assessing and collecting data for evaluation indicators can help overcome assessment and DM problems. The complex structure of real-world systems frequently leads to MADM issues, which obscure evaluation specifics. To explain uncertainty, many theories have been proposed, such as fuzzy sets (FSs) [1], which have membership grades (MG) from 0 to 1. Each element in the intuitionistic FS (IFS) developed by Atanassov [2] the condition that $0 \preceq \wp + \flat \preceq 1$, for $\wp, \flat \in [0, 1]$ and positive \wp and negative \flat . Yager [3] invented the Pythagorean FSs (PFS) concept, which is characterized by its MG and non-membership grade (NMG), with the restriction that $\wp + \flat \preceq 1$ to $\wp^2 + \flat^2 \preceq 1$. Many research have been conducted on the use of IFSs and PFSs in many fields. The constraint that the square sum of its MG and NMG degrees not exceed unity defines the extended IFSs. The concept of picture FSs is extended by FSs and IFSs [4]. Their ability to communicate information is still restricted. Because of this, the experts were still having trouble explaining the data in these sets and the associated data. Wang et al. [5] investigated the concept of complex IFS with DOMBI prioritized AOs and its application for trustworthy green supplier selection. Using the interval-valued IFS distance-based MAIRCA methodology, Mishra et al. [6] investigate a way of assessing sustainable wastewater treatment systems. Positive MG (\wp), neutral MG (α), and negative MG (\flat) are the three basic concepts of the picture FS, according to Cuong et al. [7].

Additionally, it offers more benefits than PFS and IFS. Since $\wp, \alpha, \flat \in [0, 1]$, it has been noted that the picture FS is an enhancement of the IFS that may handle more inconsistency and $0 \preceq \wp + \alpha + \flat \preceq 1$. According to the picture FS description, expert opinions like "yes," "abstain," "no," and "refusal" will be conveyed. It will also encourage uniformity between the assessment data and the actual decision environment and stop evaluation information from being thrown away. Molodtsov introduced the concept of soft sets (SOSs) [8]. SOSs more accurately the complexity and objectivity of DM in real world scenarios than other uncertain theories. Furthermore, a crucial area of study is the integration of SOSs with other mathematical models. Maji suggested FSOSs [9] and intuitionistic FSOSs [10]. Recently, Al-Husban et al. [11–14] discussed the various extension algebraic structures via FS, IVFS and AO. These two theories are used to address a range of DM problems. For the rest of the work, I shall adhere to the structure mentioned below. Section 1 deals that the introduction. Section 2 discussed PFS and its basic concepts. The new idea of 3-valued ENSSs and its fundamental functions are explained in Section 3. The similarity measures between 3-valued ENSSs are

discussed in Section 4. The selection tools for pattern recognition and its practical applications were covered in Section 5. The conclusion is covered in section 6.

2. Preliminaries

Let X be a universal set for the entirety of this section. The fundamental concepts of the neutrosophic set (NSS), which are well-known in the literature, are reviewed and introduced in this section.

Definition 2.1. The neutrosophic interval valued FS (NIVFS) $Z = \{x, \top_Z(\partial), \Im_Z(\partial), \perp_Z(\partial) | x \in X\}$, where $\top_Z(\partial) = [\top_Z^l(\partial), \top_Z^u(\partial)]$ and $\Im_Z(\partial) = [\Im_Z^l(\partial), \Im_Z^u(\partial)]$ and $\perp_Z(\partial) = [\perp_Z^l(\partial), \perp_Z^u(\partial)]$ called the value of truth, interminacy and false membership of Z , respectively. The function $\top_Z : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$, $\Im_Z : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$, $\perp_Z : X \rightarrow D[0, 1]$ and $0 \preceq (\top_Z(\partial)) + (\Im_Z(\partial)) + (\perp_Z(\partial)) \preceq 3$.

Here $Z = \langle [\top_Z^l, \top_Z^u], [\Im_Z^l, \Im_Z^u], [\perp_Z^l, \perp_Z^u] \rangle$ is mentioned a NIVF number (NIVFN).

Definition 2.2. Suppose that $Z = \langle \top_Z, \Im_Z, \perp_Z \rangle$ and $\mathcal{U} = \langle \top_{\mathcal{U}}, \Im_{\mathcal{U}}, \perp_{\mathcal{U}} \rangle$ are any two NIVFNs over (X, E) . Then

- (1) $Z^c = \langle \perp_Z, \Im_Z, \top_Z \rangle$
- (2) $Z \sqcup \mathcal{U} = \langle \max(\top_Z, \top_{\mathcal{U}}), \min(\Im_Z, \Im_{\mathcal{U}}), \min(\perp_Z, \perp_{\mathcal{U}}) \rangle$
- (3) $Z \cap \mathcal{U} = \langle \min(\top_Z, \top_{\mathcal{U}}), \min(\Im_Z, \Im_{\mathcal{U}}), \max(\perp_Z, \perp_{\mathcal{U}}) \rangle$
- (4) $Z \preceq \mathcal{U}$ iff $\top_Z \preceq \top_{\mathcal{U}}$ and $\Im_Z \preceq \Im_{\mathcal{U}}$ and $\perp_Z \succeq \perp_{\mathcal{U}}$
- (5) $Z = \mathcal{U}$ iff $\top_Z = \top_{\mathcal{U}}$ and $\Im_Z = \Im_{\mathcal{U}}$ and $\perp_Z = \perp_{\mathcal{U}}$.

Definition 2.3. Let E be a set of parameter. Given $Z \sqsubseteq E$ and $\mathcal{F} : Z \rightarrow P\mathcal{F}(X)$, where $P\mathcal{F}(X)$ is the collection of all fuzzy subsets of X , the pair (\mathcal{F}, Z) is referred to as a Pythagorean FSOS (PFSOS) on X .

Definition 2.4. A neutrosophic refined set (NRS) $Z = \{\langle x, (\top_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \top_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \top_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial)), (\Im_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \Im_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \Im_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial)), (\perp_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \perp_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \perp_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial)) \rangle : \partial \in E\}$, where, $\top_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \top_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \top_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial) : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\Im_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \Im_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \Im_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial) : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\perp_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \perp_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \dots, \perp_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial) : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $0 \preceq \top_{\frac{i}{Z}}(\partial) + \Im_{\frac{i}{Z}}(\partial) + \perp_{\frac{i}{Z}}(\partial) \preceq 3 (i = 1, 2, \dots, P)$ and $\top_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial) \preceq \top_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial) \preceq \dots \preceq \top_{\frac{i}{Z}}(\partial)$, for any $\partial \in E$. Here $\top_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \top_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \top_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial), \Im_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \Im_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \Im_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial)$ and $\perp_{\frac{1}{Z}}(\partial), \perp_{\frac{2}{Z}}(\partial), \perp_{\frac{P}{Z}}(\partial)$ represents the TMG, IMG, and FMG sequences of the element x . Additionally, P is referred to as the dimension of NRS Z . TMG sequences grow, but other sequences (IMG, FMG) do not increase or decrease. However, there is no rise or decrease in TMG, IMG, or FMG sequences throughout this paper. NRS(E) denotes the collection of all neutrosophic refined sets in E .

3. Novel approach towards 3-valued ENS

The notion of 3-valued extended neutrosophic soft sets will be presented.

Definition 3.1. Let $E = \{\kappa_1, \kappa_2, \dots, \kappa_m\}$ be a set of parameters and X be the universal set. A soft universe is the pair (X, E) . Let T and F be unchanged, and let the indeterminacy I be refined as either the same or (Unknown, contradiction), which are subsets of $[0, 1]$. Next, we obtain the 3-valued neutrosophic soft set scenario as follows:

We provide the following numerical example to demonstrate the Definition 3.1:

Example 3.2. A collection of parameters is $E = \{\kappa_1, \kappa_2, \kappa_3\}$. Assume $M : E \rightarrow M(X)$ is provided by

$$M^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.05, 0.10 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.60 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.50, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.05, 0.15 \rangle, \langle 0.40, 0.45 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.30, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.20, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.40, 0.50 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); M^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.30, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.10, 0.15 \rangle, \langle 0.50, 0.60 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.20, 0.30 \rangle, \langle 0.40, 0.50 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.30, 0.40 \rangle, \langle 0.10, 0.20 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.60 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

$$M^3(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.05, 0.10 \rangle, \langle 0.30, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.50, 0.60 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.15, 0.20 \rangle, \langle 0.40, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.40 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.05, 0.10 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.50 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

Definition 3.3. Assume that two 3-valued ENSs on (X, E) are M and N . As indicated by $M \sqsubseteq N$ if and only if $M^i(\partial) \sqsubseteq N^i(\partial)$ if $\top^i(\partial) \preceq \top^i(\partial)$, $\Im^i(\partial) \preceq \Im^i(\partial)$, $\perp^i(\partial) \succeq \perp^i(\partial)$, $\forall \partial \in X$.

We propose the following numerical example to demonstrate the previously mentioned definition:

Example 3.4. Consider the 3-valued ENS M in Example 3.2. Let N be another 3-valued ENS is defined as follows:

$$N^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.53, 0.63 \rangle, \langle 0.18, 0.38 \rangle, \langle 0.27, 0.32 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.63, 0.78 \rangle, \langle 0.18, 0.38 \rangle, \langle 0.07, 0.12 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.48, 0.68 \rangle, \langle 0.38, 0.58 \rangle, \langle 0.17, 0.22 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); N^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.48, 0.58 \rangle, \langle 0.28, 0.48 \rangle, \langle 0.12, 0.17 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.53, 0.68 \rangle, \langle 0.43, 0.68 \rangle, \langle 0.02, 0.07 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.48, 0.78 \rangle, \langle 0.38, 0.48 \rangle, \langle 0.17, 0.22 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

$$N^3(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle 0.33, 0.48 \rangle, \langle 0.48, 0.63 \rangle, \langle 0.07, 0.12 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle 0.43, 0.58 \rangle, \langle 0.68, 0.68 \rangle, \langle 0.07, 0.12 \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle 0.33, 0.58 \rangle, \langle 0.43, 0.53 \rangle, \langle 0.12, 0.17 \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

Definition 3.5. Suppose M and N are two 3-valued ENSs on (X, E) . These two 3-valued ENSs are identical (denoted by $M = N$) if and only if $M^i \sqsubseteq N^i$ and $M^i \supseteq N^i$.

Definition 3.6. Let M and N denote two 3-valued ENSs on (X, E) . The union and intersection of M and N over (X, E) are indicated by $M \sqcup N$ and $M \sqcap N$, respectively, $J : E \rightarrow M(X)$, $I : E \rightarrow M(X)$ such that $J(\partial) = M(\partial) \sqcup N(\partial)$, $I(\partial) = M(\partial) \sqcap N(\partial)$, for all $\partial \in X$.

Example 3.7. Let M and N be the two 3-valued ENSs on (X, E) that are defined as

$$M^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.50), (0.20,0.30), (0.30,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.40), (0.50,0.60), (0.30,0.40) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.60), (0.20,0.40), (0.20,0.30) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); M^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.50), (0,0.10), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.40), (0.10,0.30), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.40,0.60), (0.10,0.20), (0.30,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

and

$$N^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.40), (0.20,0.40), (0.40,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.30), (0,0.20), (0.50,0.70) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.40,0.50), (0.30,0.40), (0.20,0.30) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); N^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.10,0.40), (0.20,0.30), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.30), (0.30,0.40), (0.40,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.40), (0.30,0.50), (0.40,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

$$M^1(\partial) \sqcup N^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.50), (0.20,0.30), (0.30,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.40), (0,0.20), (0.30,0.40) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.40,0.60), (0.20,0.40), (0.20,0.30) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); M^2(\partial) \sqcup N^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.50), (0,0.10), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.40), (0.10,0.30), (0.40,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.40,0.60), (0.10,0.20), (0.30,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

$$M^1(\partial) \sqcap N^1(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.40), (0.20,0.30), (0.40,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.30), (0,0.20), (0.50,0.70) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.30,0.50), (0.20,0.40), (0.20,0.30) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right); M^2(\partial) \sqcap N^2(\partial) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \frac{\kappa_1}{\langle\langle (0.10,0.40), (0,0.10), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_2}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.30), (0.10,0.30), (0.50,0.60) \rangle\rangle} \\ \frac{\kappa_3}{\langle\langle (0.20,0.40), (0.10,0.20), (0.40,0.50) \rangle\rangle} \end{array} \right);$$

4. Determine similarity measure

Methods: Let Z and Y be the two 3-valued ENSs. The similarity measure between Z and Y is defined as $Sim(Z, Y) = \Phi(Z, Y)$. Since

$$\Phi(Z, Y) = \frac{1}{n'n} \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\begin{array}{c} \min \left\{ T_1^l(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)), T_2^l(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)), S^l(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)) \right\}, \\ \max \left\{ T_1^u(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)), T_2^u(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)), S^u(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)) \right\} \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

and $T_1(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)) =$

$$\left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Z^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_Y^{il}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{(1 - \top_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k))})}, \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_Y^{iu}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{(1 - \top_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k))})} \right) \quad (2)$$

$T_2(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)) =$

$$\left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\Im_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \Im_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{(1 - \Im_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \Im_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k))})}, \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\Im_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \Im_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{(1 - \Im_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \Im_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k))})} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$S(Z(\partial_k), Y(\partial_k)) = \left(1 - \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\uparrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \uparrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n'+1} (\uparrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k))}, \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\uparrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \uparrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^{n'+1} (\uparrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|} \right) \tag{4}$$

Theorem 4.1. Let Z, Y and W denote any three 3-valued ENSs over (X, E) . Show that $Z \sqsubseteq Y \sqsubseteq W \implies Sim(Z, W) \preceq Sim(Y, W)$.

Proof. For $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, n'$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Z \sqsubseteq Y &\implies \left\{ \begin{aligned} \left(\uparrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\uparrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\downarrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\succeq \left(\downarrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ Z \sqsubseteq W &\implies \left\{ \begin{aligned} \left(\uparrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\mathfrak{S}_W^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\downarrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\succeq \left(\downarrow_W^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ Y \sqsubseteq W &\implies \left\{ \begin{aligned} \left(\uparrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k), \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\preceq \left(\mathfrak{S}_W^{il}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \\ \left(\downarrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) &\succeq \left(\downarrow_W^{il}(\partial_k), \downarrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{5}$$

Clearly,

$$\left(\left(\uparrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right), \left(\uparrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \right) \preceq \left(\left(\uparrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right), \left(\uparrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \right)$$

$$\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\uparrow_Z^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\uparrow_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \right) \preceq \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\uparrow_Y^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\uparrow_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \uparrow_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right) \right) \tag{6}$$

Clearly,

$$\left(\uparrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \preceq \left(\uparrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k), \uparrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \preceq \left(\uparrow_W^{i2l}(\partial_k), \uparrow_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

and

$$\left(-\uparrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k), -\uparrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(-\uparrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k), -\uparrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(-\uparrow_W^{i2u}(\partial_k), -\uparrow_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right)$$

and

$$\left(\downarrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(\downarrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(\downarrow_W^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

and

$$\left(\left(\left(\downarrow_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \cdot \left(\downarrow_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right), \left(\left(\downarrow_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \cdot \left(\downarrow_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right) \right) \succeq \left(\left(\left(\downarrow_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \cdot \left(\downarrow_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right), \left(\left(\downarrow_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \cdot \left(\downarrow_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right) \right)$$

and

$$\left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \succeq \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & 1 - \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \preceq \\ & 1 - \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \\ & \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)}, 1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \preceq \\ & \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)}, 1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\left\{ \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right) \preceq \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right) \right\} \tag{7}$$

Equations (6) is divided by (7),

$$\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\tau_Z^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \tau_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right)}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right)}, \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\tau_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \tau_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right)}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right)} \succeq \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\tau_Y^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \tau_W^{il}(\partial_k) \right)}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right)}, \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\tau_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \tau_W^{iu}(\partial_k) \right)}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \tau_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \tau_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right)}$$

Hence

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Z^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_W^{il}(\partial_k)) \right)}{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{((1 - \top_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)))}) \right)} \right), \frac{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Z^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_W^{iu}(\partial_k)) \right)}{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{((1 - \top_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)))}) \right)} \right) \right\} \succcurlyeq \left\{ \left(\frac{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Y^{il}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_W^{il}(\partial_k)) \right)}{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{((1 - \top_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)))}) \right)} \right), \frac{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\top_Y^{iu}(\partial_k) \cdot \top_W^{iu}(\partial_k)) \right)}{\left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (1 - \sqrt{((1 - \top_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \top_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)))}) \right)} \right) \right\}; \tag{8}$$

Therefore

$$T_1(Z(\partial_k), W(\partial_k)) \preceq T_1(Y(\partial_k), W(\partial_k))$$

Clearly,

$$\left((\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \preceq \left((\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \\ & \preceq \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Clearly,

$$\left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right) \preceq \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right) \preceq \left(\mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

implies that

$$\left(-\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k), -\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(-\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k), -\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(-\mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k), -\mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k) \right)$$

$$\left(1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k), 1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k), 1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k), 1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k))), ((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k))) \right) \succeq \\ & \left(((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k))), ((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k))) \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \succeq \\
 & \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \\
 & 1 - \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \preceq \\
 & 1 - \left(\sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)}, \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \\
 & \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)}, 1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \preceq \\
 & \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)}, 1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \\
 & \left\{ \left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right) \succeq \right\} \\
 & \left\{ \left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right) \right\}; \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation (9) is divided by (10),

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)} \succeq \\
 & \frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right), \oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\left\{ \left(\frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)}, \frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Z^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)} \right) \succeq \right\}; \\
 \left\{ \left(\frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4l}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)}, \frac{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(\mathfrak{S}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathfrak{S}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right)}{\left(\oplus_{k=1}^{n'} \oplus_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \sqrt{\left((1 - \mathfrak{S}_Y^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \cdot (1 - \mathfrak{S}_W^{i4u}(\partial_k)) \right)} \right) \right)} \right) \right\};$$

Therefore

$$T_2(Z(\partial_k), W(\partial_k)) \preceq T_2(Y(\partial_k), W(\partial_k)) \tag{11}$$

Clearly,

$$\left(\mathfrak{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(\mathfrak{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(\mathfrak{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k), \mathfrak{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

and

$$\left(\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) - \left(\downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \succeq \left(\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) - \left(\downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right)$$

implies

$$\left| \left(\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) - \left(\downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right| \succeq \left| \left(\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) - \left(\downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k), \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k) \right) \right|$$

$$\left| \left(\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k), \downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right| \succeq \left| \left(\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k), \downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k) \right) \right|$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \\ & \succeq \left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Also,

$$\left((\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \succeq \left((\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right)$$

implies that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left((\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \succeq \left| \left((\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \\ & \left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \\ & \succeq \left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right| \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Equations (12) is divided by (13), we get

$$\frac{\left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right) \right|}{\left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right|} \succeq \frac{\left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)) \right) \right|}{\left| \left(\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2l}(\partial_k)), \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n 1 + (\downarrow_y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \downarrow_w^{i2u}(\partial_k)) \right) \right|}$$

implies that

$$\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right| \succeq$$

$$\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|$$

and

$$\sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} , \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|} \succeq$$

$$\sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} , \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|}$$

and

$$\left(1 - \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} , \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Z^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|} \right) \preceq$$

$$\left(1 - \sqrt{\left| \left(\frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2u}(\partial_k))} , \frac{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2u}(\partial_k) - \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))}{\bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n (\mathcal{J}_Y^{i2l}(\partial_k) \cdot \mathcal{J}_W^{i2l}(\partial_k))} \right) \right|} \right)$$

Therefore

$$S(Z(\partial_k), W(\partial_k)) \preceq S(Y(\partial_k), W(\partial_k)) \tag{14}$$

Hence

$$\Phi(Z, W) \preceq \Phi(Y, W) \tag{15}$$

Hence $Sim(Z, W) \preceq Sim(Y, W)$.

Example 4.2. Determine the similarity measure between Z and Y , the two 3-valued ENSs.

$Z(\partial_k)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$Z^1(\partial_k)$	(0.43,0.45),(0.35,0.4),(0.55,0.6)	(0.63,0.7),(0.1,0.15),(0.35,0.5)	(0.53,0.55),(0.4,0.55),(0.2,0.3)
$Z^2(\partial_k)$	(0.35,0.65),(0.25,0.3),(0.5,0.65)	(0.25,0.55),(0.1,0.25),(0.5,0.6)	(0.1,0.25),(0.35,0.5),(0.65,0.75)
$Z^3(\partial_k)$	(0.2,0.3),(0.5,0.55),(0.45,0.65)	(0.15,0.2),(0.4,0.45),(0.4,0.6)	(0.35,0.5),(0.6,0.65),(0.6,0.75)
$Y(\partial_k)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$Y^1(\partial_k)$	(0.25,0.55),(0.25,0.4),(0.3,0.35)	(0.55,0.6),(0.35,0.45),(0.2,0.25)	(0.5,0.7),(0.25,0.35),(0.1,0.35)
$Y^2(\partial_k)$	(0.6,0.65),(0.5,0.65),(0.1,0.2)	(0.5,0.6),(0.35,0.5),(0.3,0.35)	(0.4,0.5),(0.2,0.6),(0.2,0.4)
$Y^3(\partial_k)$	(0.3,0.35),(0.35,0.4),(0.15,0.2)	(0.4,0.55),(0.2,0.25),(0.1,0.3)	(0.5,0.6),(0.25,0.35),(0.25,0.35)

Using methods and routine calculation, we get

$$T_1(Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)) = (0.967871, 0.968767), T_2(Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)) = (0.592525, 0.66815) \text{ and}$$

$$S(Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)) = (0.570274, 0.773526).$$

Now,

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \min \left\{ T_1^l (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)), T_2^l (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)), S^l (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)) \right\}, \\ \max \left\{ T_1^u (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)), T_2^u (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)), S^u (Z^1(\partial_k), Y^1(\partial_k)) \right\} \end{array} \right) = (0.570274, 0.968767).$$

Similarly, $T_1 (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)) = (0.74977, 0.958134)$,

$T_2 (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)) = (0.438915, 0.631053)$ and

$S (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)) = (0.370608, 0.563633)$.

Now,

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \min \left\{ T_1^l (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)), T_2^l (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)), S^l (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)) \right\}, \\ \max \left\{ T_1^u (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)), T_2^u (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)), S^u (Z^2(\partial_k), Y^2(\partial_k)) \right\} \end{array} \right) = (0.370608, 0.958134).$$

Similarly, $T_1 (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)) = (0.847848, 0.86513)$,

$T_2 (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)) = (0.48955, 0.619081)$ and

$S (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)) = (0.357564, 0.611763)$.

Now,

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} \min \left\{ T_1^l (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)), T_2^l (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)), S^l (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)) \right\}, \\ \max \left\{ T_1^u (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)), T_2^u (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)), S^u (Z^3(\partial_k), Y^3(\partial_k)) \right\} \end{array} \right) = (0.357564, 0.86513).$$

Hence, $Sim(Z, Y) = (0.144272, 0.310226)$.

5. Pattern recognition problem solving by 3-valued ENS model

A system's capacity to recognize patterns and regularities in data through information analysis is known as pattern recognition. It is helpful in domains like computer vision, health care, security, and automation because it enables systems to categorize, group, and analyze complicated datasets. Some of its real-world applications will be covered in this article.

- (1) Machine vision: In order to comprehend and make judgments based on visual input, machine vision uses cameras, sensors, and algorithms to take, process, and analyze images. By searching for particular characteristics like forms, colors, and textures that can be used to identify items and spot flaws, it finds patterns in photos.
- (2) Computer aided diagnosis (CAD): Pattern recognition is used by Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems to evaluate medical images and help physicians diagnose illnesses. It employs sophisticated algorithms to identify patterns in medical images that mirror recognized symptoms of diseases including tumors, fractures, or abnormal tissues. Examples of these images include X-rays, CT scans, and MRIs. These trends point to possible problem areas that physicians should look at.
- (3) Speech recognition: The ability of a machine to recognize spoken words and translate them into written text is known as speech recognition. It enables machines to comprehend human speech by using pattern recognition to identify speech patterns, including words, noises, and

pauses. This method converts audio into text by breaking the audio signal up into parts and then utilizing those segments to match speech patterns to a database of recognized words.

- (4) Character recognition: Optical Character Recognition (OCR), another name for character recognition, is a pattern recognition method that turns scanned text images into editable and searchable text. Physical document digitization is a common usage for it. OCR systems match known characters with the shapes of letters, numbers, and symbols in a scanned image. After that, the system turns these forms into machine-readable text.
- (5) Financial sector: In the financial industry, pattern recognition is crucial for identifying fraud, analyzing stock market movements, and determining credit risk. It examines transaction data in order to spot odd trends and actions that might point to fraud. By identifying past trends and projecting future price changes, it also aids in stock market trend forecasting.

5.1. Algorithms for 3-valued ENS Model

Using the 3-valued ENS model, an algorithm for DM problems is described.

Step 1. Enter the ENS in tabular form with three values.

Step 2. Determine the values of $T_1^i(\partial_k)$, $\top_2^i(\partial_k)$ and $S^i(\partial_k)$, $1 \preceq j \preceq n$ and $1 \preceq j \preceq m$.

Step 3. Find similarity measure =

$$\Phi = \frac{1}{n'n} \bigoplus_{k=1}^{n'} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n \left(\min\{T_1^{il}(\partial_k), T_2^{il}(\partial_k), S^{il}(\partial_k)\}, \max\{T_1^{iu}(\partial_k), T_2^{iu}(\partial_k), S^{iu}(\partial_k)\} \right).$$

Step 4. Choose a similarity measure when the conditions for being considerably similar are met.

Step 5. Finally, make a decision regarding the problem.

Step 6. End.

5.2. Data Analysis

Suppose that there are five types of pattern recognition P, Q, R, S and T . Were the set of parameters E represented by $E = \{e_1 : \text{Accuracy and speed}, e_2 : \text{Generalization and robustness}, e_3 : \text{Feature extraction and selection}, e_4 : \text{Classification and decision making}, e_5 : \text{Adaptability and learning}\}$, where $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Tables 1 and 2 provide the ideal values (L) of pattern recognition.

TABLE 1. Ideal values

$L(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$L^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.55, 0.75 \rangle, \langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.65 \rangle$	$\langle 0.45, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.65 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$
$L^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.65 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.6, 0.7 \rangle$	$\langle 0.65, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.65, 0.7 \rangle$
$L^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$

TABLE 2. Ideal values

$L(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$L^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.5, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle$
$L^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.65, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$
$L^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.5 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle$

We create 3-valued ENSSs for pattern recognition, as shown in Tables 3 to 12.

TABLE 3. 3-valued ENS for the machine vision P^i

$P(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$P^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.45 \rangle$
$P^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$
$P^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$

TABLE 4. Ideal values

$P(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$P^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.15, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle$
$P^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$
$P^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle$

TABLE 5. 3-valued ENS for the computer aided diagnosis Q^i

$Q(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$Q^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.15, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle$
$Q^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.2, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$
$Q^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$

TABLE 6. 3-valued ENS for the computer aided diagnosis Q^i

$Q(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$Q^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.55 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1, 0.15 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle$
$Q^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$
$Q^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.5, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$

TABLE 7. 3-valued ENS for the speech recognition R^i

$R(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$R^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$
$R^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$
$R^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$

TABLE 8. 3-valued ENS for the speech recognition R^i

$R(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$R^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.2, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$
$R^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$
$R^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.6, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.35 \rangle$

TABLE 9. 3-valued ENS for the character recognition S^i

$S(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$S^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.45 \rangle$
$S^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$
$S^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$

TABLE 10. 3-valued ENS for the character recognition S^i

$S(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$S^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.1, 0.15 \rangle$	$\langle 0.6, 0.65 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$
$S^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle$	$\langle 0.45, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.2 \rangle$
$S^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.4 \rangle$

TABLE 11. 3-valued ENS for the financial sector T^i

$T(\partial)$	κ_1	κ_2	κ_3
$T^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle$
$T^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.25 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$
$T^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.2 \rangle$	$\langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.35, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle$	0.45, 0.5, 0.25, 0.3, 0.3, 0.45

TABLE 12. 3-valued ENS for the financial sector T^i

$T(\partial)$	κ_4	κ_5
$T^1(\partial)$	$\langle 0.3, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.65, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.4 \rangle$	$\langle 0.25, 0.35 \rangle, \langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$
$T^2(\partial)$	$\langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.45, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.25, 0.45 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.45 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.7 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.5 \rangle$
$T^3(\partial)$	$\langle 0.5, 0.55 \rangle, \langle 0.15, 0.4 \rangle, \langle 0.2, 0.3 \rangle$	$\langle 0.4, 0.5 \rangle, \langle 0.55, 0.6 \rangle, \langle 0.3, 0.35 \rangle$

The experts present the 3-valued ENS and its values in Tables 3 to 12, based on their assessment of the alternatives against the criteria under discussion. In this example, we should compute the similarity measure of the 3-valued ENSs in Table 3 to Table 12 with the one in Table 1 using method. The similarity measure for pattern recognition P^i to T^i is calculated as shown in the table below.

Tables 13 and 14 show different values.

TABLE 13. Different values

	$T_1^1(x_1)$	$T_2^1(x_1)$	$S^1(x_1)$	$T_1^2(x_2)$	$T_2^2(x_2)$
(L, P)	$\langle 0.800316, 0.84237 \rangle$	$\langle 0.758793, 0.762018 \rangle$	$\langle 0.509328, 0.765444 \rangle$	$\langle 0.671653, 0.740835 \rangle$	$\langle 0.70213, 0.791527 \rangle$
(L, Q)	$\langle 0.719578, 0.794162 \rangle$	$\langle 0.792615, 0.873883 \rangle$	$\langle 0.84641, 0.579972 \rangle$	$\langle 0.916231, 0.932051 \rangle$	$\langle 0.844602, 0.866913 \rangle$
(L, R)	$\langle 0.895836, 0.91482 \rangle$	$\langle 0.867642, 0.895062 \rangle$	$\langle 0.648341, 0.923459 \rangle$	$\langle 0.888981, 0.935176 \rangle$	$\langle 0.557979, 0.741576 \rangle$
(L, S)	$\langle 0.781427, 0.819973 \rangle$	$\langle 0.679001, 0.781781 \rangle$	$\langle 0.477713, 0.693705 \rangle$	$\langle 0.854992, 0.884033 \rangle$	$\langle 0.550141, 0.763987 \rangle$
(L, T)	$\langle 0.939365, 0.948507 \rangle$	$\langle 0.728212, 0.806633 \rangle$	$\langle 0.512322, 0.737975 \rangle$	$\langle 0.869847, 0.895939 \rangle$	$\langle 0.785653, 0.815063 \rangle$

TABLE 14. Different values

	$S^2(x_2)$	$T_1^3(x_3)$	$T_2^3(x_3)$	$S^3(x_3)$	Similarity
(L, P)	$\langle 0.535115, 0.893521 \rangle$	$\langle 0.652244, 0.706035 \rangle$	$\langle 0.470374, 0.533671 \rangle$	$\langle 0.481875, 0.652386 \rangle$	0.142049
(L, Q)	$\langle 0.457751, 0.574692 \rangle$	$\langle 0.782963, 0.865623 \rangle$	$\langle 0.700021, 0.790201 \rangle$	$\langle 0.463118, 0.589981 \rangle$	0.143720
(L, R)	$\langle 0.600575, 0.865618 \rangle$	$\langle 0.856691, 0.877117 \rangle$	$\langle 0.665936, 0.684441 \rangle$	$\langle 0.595246, 0.773675 \rangle$	0.132584
(L, S)	$\langle 0.46486, 0.572492 \rangle$	$\langle 0.802296, 0.841273 \rangle$	$\langle 0.709213, 0.794079 \rangle$	$\langle 0.676507, 0.950697 \rangle$	0.14246
(L, T)	$\langle 0.478567, 0.666398 \rangle$	$\langle 0.828071, 0.890342 \rangle$	$\langle 0.73, 0.82751 \rangle$	$\langle 0.640519, 0.901223 \rangle$	0.145903

The pattern recognition similarity measure follows the order $T > Q > S > P > R$, as shown in the preceding results. As a result, we conclude that the patient T represents the best alternative.

6. Conclusion

The primary purpose of this study is to provide a three-valued ENS and investigate some of its features. The similarity measure of two 3-valued ENS is addressed, and an example of rel-life is shown. In the future, we shall use the generalized hesitant cubic fuzzy soft sets and generalized hesitant intervalued fuzzy soft sets theories.

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